

A STUDY ON CONSUMERS SATISFACTION ON BRAND PREFERENCE OF MERIIBOY ICE CREAM WITH SPECIAL REFERANCE TO PALAKKAD DISTRICT

¹Mr. P. Vishnu, ²Ms. K.S. Shymili

¹III-B.com, Banking, Nehru Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.

²Assistant Professor, Department of B.Com Banking, Nehru Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18936498>

Published Date: 10-March-2026

Abstract: This study examines the consumer preference towards Merii Boy ice cream among customers in the Palakkad region. The research aims to identify the factors influencing buying behavior such as taste, price, quality, and brand awareness. Primary data were collected from 110 respondents using a structured questionnaire. Statistical tools like percentage analysis, chi-square test, and regression analysis were used to interpret the data. The study also analyses customer satisfaction and brand loyalty towards Merii Boy ice cream. Findings highlight the importance of product quality, flavor variety, and promotional strategies in shaping consumer preference. The results help marketers understand consumer behavior and improve marketing strategies to enhance customer satisfaction and brand competitiveness.

Keywords: Consumer Preference, Buying Behavior, Ice Cream Industry, Brand Loyalty.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the stage of primitive economy, every individual, family or a social unit used to produce all that was necessary for their consumption. That means they were self-sufficient. Due to the advancement in science and technology more and more competitors emerged in the market with new variety of products. So, it has become obligatory from the part of existing manufacture to maintain a cordial and satisfactory relationship with. Customers who will have certain expectations prior to the purchase known as customers. These expectations may be nature and performance of the product. The cost and efforts to be spent before obtaining the direct product or service benefits. The social benefits accruing to the customers because of the products.

Preference: Preference is a kind of stepping away from the experience and evaluating it. One could have a pleasurable experience that caused dissatisfaction because even though pleasurable, it was not an emotion, it is the evaluation of an emotion. Consumer Behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, organization select, buy, use and dispose of goods or services to satisfy their needs and wants. A consumer's buying behavior is influenced by cultural, social, and personal factors. The social factors include reference groups, opinion leader, and family while the personal factors include age, occupation etc. The measure of behavioral aspect of consumers can be done on various parameters such as occasions of purchase, benefits of using the products, consumer status towards usage of the product, there at eat which the consumer consumes the product, the loyalty status of the consumer, finally the attitude of the consumers towards the product. The demographic variable includes age, Family size, gender, income, occupation, education. The buying behavior is the impact of buyer's decision-making process. The buying decision process involves five stages. The first stage is the problem

recognition. At this stage, a need is triggered by internal or external stimuli. The second stage is information search. The sources of information may be personal, commercial, Public, experimental. The next stage is Evaluation of alternatives and then the purchase decisions and the final stage is post-purchase behavior. Overall, the study on buying behavior of the product will help oneself to understand the degree of involvement of consumer towards the product. It is a concept, used in the social sciences, particularly economics. It assumes a real or imagined "choice" between alternatives and the possibility of rank ordering of these alternatives, based on happiness, satisfaction, gratification, enjoyment, utility they provide. More generally, it can be seen as a source of motivation. In cognitive sciences, individual preferences enable choice of objectives/goals.

2. OBJECTIVE

- To study the preference of customers towards different varieties of Meriiboy ice cream.
- To know various factors affecting customers buying behavior towards Meriiboy ice cream.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- Research Design : Descriptive research design was adopted.
- Area of Study : Palakkad District.
- Sample Size : 110 respondents.
- Sampling Technique : Convenient sampling.
- Data Collection : Primary data through questionnaires; secondary data from journals and websites.
- Statistical Tools Used : Percentage analysis, Chi-square test, and Regression analysis.
- Period of Study : 3 months

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

AGE * CONSUMPTION OF ICE CREAM

Age * Consumption of ice cream Cross tabulation						
Count						
		Consumption of ice cream				Total
		Enthusiastic	Neutral	Indifferent	negative	
age	below 15	0	0	3	3	6
	16-25	60	20	4	0	84
	26-35	15	0	0	0	15
	Above 36	5	0	0	0	5
Total		80	20	7	3	110

Chi-square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	84.184 ^a	9	.000
Likelihood Ratio	48.864	9	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	24.979	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	110		
a. 12 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.			

- There Is A Significant Relationship Between the Age of The Respondents and Consumption of Ice Cream by The Respondents.

5. CONCLUSION

This study is entitled to “A study on consumer preference towards Merii boy ice-creams” the overall analysis of study indicates that at present most of the customer are satisfied towards Merii boy ice creams. The study is useful for understanding the respondent’s preference while choosing the ice cream. The latest trend in ice cream is mixing of tradition with rich creams. The preference of the respondents while choosing the ice creams based on different attribute is studied.

In modern world, people desired attractive and quality brand. They need quality, taste with reasonable price. Therefore, the concern must follow the new sales promotion method. Manufacture or dealers provide various free offers method and create highly demand for their brand in the market field. The knowledge of satisfaction level of Ice cream would render immense help to the companies in planning and implementing marketing strategies. An attempt is made to identify the level of awareness and market perception among the respondents towards Merii boy ice cream. It was found during studies that Merii boy has a very good market reputation in Palakkad. They have a huge market share and big customer base. They have a bright future as have many uncovered area and potential customers.

Merii boy is using very good strategy of selling their products. They do have product diversification, which have advantage of expansion of network and advantage of each underline objectives. Products are available for all most all the segment. Merri boy caters to all segments and more popular in Kerala. It has a huge variety of ice creams with a huge base of flavors despite of all these factors Merii boy is not among the top of the choices of the consumer (mainly young students and working class, according to the data collected until now). The people or the respondents have rated high for Merii boy ice cream for its variety, flavor and quality. It has been highly rated as “inexpensive” too. However, the appearance is something Merii boy need to work upon, which was the only factor our respondents were not satisfied about. The point of dilemma here arises is that though people are very well aware of Merii boy ice creams their taste, quality, appearance still they do not prefer to be a loyal customer or go for it more times as they do for their favorite brand. Therefore, at this stage, all I can say is that Merii boy needs to work upon as a more visible brand. It needs to work more upon their advertisements intensity and offers and come out strong as a complete package towards the potential customers they are missing.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Sivaram, “Factors influencing consumption pattern of ice cream in Bengaluru market,” *Indian Journal of Dairy Science*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 432–437, 2016.
- [2] S. Priyadarshini, S. Gandhimathi, and P. Vimalkumar, “A study on consumer preference and satisfaction towards Arun Ice-Creams,” *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 15–19, Apr. 2021.
- [3] T. S. Wibowo, J. Sudewa, D. N. Misidawati, P. Afriyeni, N. Normansyah, and M. Rizki, “The effect of market segmentation and customer preference on customer satisfaction of Ice Cream Mixue in Yogyakarta,” *International Journal of Economics Development Research*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1–10, 2023.
- [4] R. D. Melati and Sumiati, “Analysis of consumer preferences towards ice cream products using conjoint analysis,” *Jurnal Kewirausahaan dan Inovasi*, 2025.
- [5] F. A. Castillo Placencia, H. Y. Lindao Narváez, I. M. Fejoo Jaramillo, and C. B. Sarmiento Chugcho, “The role of sensory marketing in ice cream parlor purchase decisions,” *Revista Universidad de Guayaquil*, 2024.
- [6] A. A. Neto da Silva, K. O. Batista, R. A. B. Monteiro Araújo, and R. A. Bastos, “Ice cream: Consumer opinion and behavior,” *Research, Society and Development*, vol. 12, no. 9, 2023.
- [7] K. Kalavadia and R. Debnath, “Analyzing the attributes for ice cream purchase decisions among Generation Z consumers,” *Indian Journal of Marketing*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 76–90, 2024.
- [8] J. A. Martin, “Consumer preference of vanilla ice cream,” M.S. thesis, Dept. of Dietetics and Human Nutrition, University of Kentucky, Lexington, KY, USA, 2018.
- [9] P. Kotler and K. L. Keller, *Marketing Management*, 15th ed. New Delhi, India: Pearson Education, 2016.
- [10] L. G. Schiffman and J. L. Wisenblit, *Consumer Behavior*, 12th ed. Boston, MA, USA: Pearson Education, 2019.